

Are Large Language Models Smart Coders? Evaluating Correctness and Efficiency of LLM-generated Algorithms

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Abstract: Skilled software developers play a crucial role in creating energy-efficient code, contributing to the reduction of carbon emissions and promoting sustainable computing practices. In parallel, Large Language Models (LLMs) have recently emerged as powerful programming assistants, providing support for developers in complex coding tasks. In this context, this study investigates the ability of LLMs to generate computationally efficient implementations of classic algorithms - such as Heap Sort and Binary Search - across different programming languages, with a primary focus on optimizing energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time. Our results show that, in most cases, different LLMs are able to generate these algorithm implementations correctly. Furthermore, in the majority of the evaluated scenarios, LLM-generated code demonstrates superior performance over human-written algorithm code with regard to energy consumption, memory efficiency, and execution time.

Keywords: LLM, Correctness, Energy-efficiency, Memory-efficiency, Time-efficiency.

Categories: H.3.1, H.3.2, H.3.3, H.3.7, H.5.1

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1 Introduction

In recent years, the investigation into reducing the environmental impact of software has gained increasing attention [Guldner et al. 2024, Kern et al. 2018]. This growing interest reflects the need to understand how software development and usage can be optimized to minimize environmental harm—particularly through the efficient use of computational resources such as energy and memory [Paul et al. 2023]. In 2020, data centers, communication networks, and end-user devices were collectively responsible for an estimated 4–6% of global electricity consumption, rising to 5–8% when televisions are included [Ross and Christie 2022, Malmodin and Lundén 2018]. While projections vary, there is consensus that the energy demand of the technology sector will continue to rise in the coming years [Andrae 2020].

Additionally, the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) to enhance developer productivity has also gained increasing attention [Liu et al. 2023, Mendoza et al. 2024,

Donato et al. 2025, Fagadau et al. 2024]. These models are increasingly employed as programming assistants, capable of supporting developers in a variety of coding tasks [AWS 2024, Hunts.AI 2024, BlackBox AI 2024, OpenAI 2024, Google 2024, GitHub 2024]. Recently, developers have been focusing on using LLMs for direct code generation, which raises concerns about the correctness of this code [Corso et al. 2024a, Bui et al. 2025, Liu et al. 2023]. In parallel, considering the environmental impact of software, it becomes essential to evaluate the efficiency of LLM-generated code in terms of energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time.

In this context, we investigate whether LLMs are capable of generating correct code in three programming languages: Java, Python, and C. Specifically, we focus on ten classical algorithms, including Heap Sort, Binary Search, and Dijkstra's algorithm. Additionally, we evaluate the energy efficiency, memory usage, and execution time of the LLM-generated implementations. Our investigation consists of two phases. First, we generate these algorithm implementations by prompting five freely available LLMs in GroqCloud [GroqCloud 2025] to avoid user context bias from influencing the responses. Second, to obtain results from a real user perspective, we prompt six LLM-based code assistant applications, such as Copilot and ChatGPT. Then, we measure the rate of correctly generated algorithm code, energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time. Furthermore, we compare the obtained results with human-written code from The Rosetta Code [Rosetta Code 2025] and The Algorithms [The Algorithms 2025].

Our results indicate that both GroqCloud models and LLM-based code assistant applications are capable of generating correct algorithm implementations, achieving at least 97% of correct responses. In terms of energy efficiency, LLM-generated code tends to outperform human-written code. However, no single GroqCloud model or application consistently delivers the best results across all measures. In contrast, for memory usage, LLMs do not consistently outperform human implementations. Notably, human-written Python code exhibits lower memory consumption compared to its LLM-generated counterparts. Additionally, while LLM-generated code demonstrates better execution times in Python and C, human-written code performs better in Java. At last, we identify correlations between energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time for GroqCloud models. However, unexpectedly, our findings indicate a weak correlation for these metrics regarding LLM-based code assistant applications.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 presents the study design, including the research questions and the measurement model. Section 4 reports our findings on correctness, energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time. We also discuss potential threats to validity. Finally, Section 5 concludes this work.

2 Related Work

Rashid et al. [Rashid et al. 2015] analyze the energy efficiency of several sorting algorithms implemented in different programming languages on ARM-based devices, specifically using a Raspberry Pi¹. They measure the energy consumption of the execution of algorithms such as Bubble Sort, Merge Sort, Quick Sort, and Counting Sort, highlighting how these implementations impact energy usage, computational performance, and memory management. In contrast, our work includes LLM-generated algorithm implementations as well as non-sorting algorithms, such as Dijkstra's, AVL Tree, and Queue. This allows us to evaluate the impact of human-written code compared to

¹ <https://www.raspberrypi.com/>

LLM-generated solutions, providing a broader perspective on the efficiency of different programming approaches, including those executed on an Intel-based processor using Intel's RAPL [David et al. 2010, Intel 2024].

Corso et al. [Corso et al. 2024b] analyze Java methods generated by LLM-based code assistant applications (e.g., ChatGPT and Gemini), focusing on the syntactic and semantic correctness, complexity, efficiency, and size of the generated code. Their study draws from Java projects on GitHub, utilizing tools such as Antlr [Parr 2024] and DependencyFinder [Tessier 2024] to process real-world methods. They select these methods based on specific criteria, including being tested and documented, and they are validated through test suites. This approach emphasizes the complexity and correctness of the generated code within real software development contexts. Conversely, our work focuses on resource consumption — specifically energy, memory, and execution time — when running LLM-generated algorithm implementations. While we also compare LLM-generated code with human-written code, our primary concern is how efficiently the code uses computational resources, with an emphasis on green computing and sustainability. Furthermore, instead of focusing on software project methods, we analyze classic algorithms across different programming languages, broadening the scope of the evaluation to include both human and LLM-generated implementations.

Pereira et al. [Pereira et al. 2017] evaluate the runtime performance, memory usage, and energy consumption of 27 programming languages. Their analysis is based on ten algorithms implemented in each language, sourced from the Computer Language Benchmarks Game (CLBG) [Gouy 2024]. The study presents comparative results, highlighting which languages tend to perform faster or slower, consume more or less energy, and utilize more or less memory. On the other hand, our work measures these factors and also includes memory usage as a key metric. Additionally, we extend the analysis by incorporating LLM-generated implementations of the algorithms, comparing them directly with human-written code. This allows us to assess both the impact of different programming languages and the efficiency of LLM-generated versus human-generated implementations of such algorithms.

Couto et al. [Couto et al. 2017b] conducted a study focused on the energy efficiency of different programming languages, comparing the runtime and energy consumption of ten well-known programming languages. Their work uses benchmarks from the Computer Language Benchmarks Game (CLBG) [Gouy 2024] and monitors the energy consumed during the execution of algorithms implemented in each language using Intel's RAPL tool [David et al. 2010, Intel 2024]. This study provides a ranking of programming languages based on energy efficiency, focusing on compiled and interpreted languages. While our study shares the goal of analyzing energy consumption and runtime, a key difference lies in the approach: we use LLM accessed via the Groq API and LLM-based code assistant applications to generate the implementations of the algorithms, whereas Couto et al. [Couto et al. 2017b] rely on human-written benchmarks from the CLBG. We emphasize the comparison between LLM-generated and human-written code in terms of energy efficiency, memory usage, and runtime.

Georgiou et al. [Georgiou et al. 2017] measure energy consumption and runtime performance of 14 programming languages using a set of tasks from the Rosetta Code repository [Rosetta Code 2025]. This study compares compiled, semi-compiled, and interpreted languages, focusing on their efficiency in terms of energy consumption and execution time across different tasks. They conclude that compiled languages are generally more energy-efficient than interpreted ones and found that Java's energy consumption did not significantly diverge from that of C and C++. Our results align with this observation, as we find that LLM-generated Java code can be highly efficient,

with models like gemma2 and assistants like Codeium producing implementations that outperform even human-written code. Furthermore, Georgiou et al. note that Python implementations contribute to high energy consumption. While our analysis of human-written Python code from repositories sometimes supports this, we also demonstrate that LLM-generated Python code can be energy-efficient, as seen with the Codeium assistant. This suggests that while the choice of language is important, as established by Georgiou et al., the source of implementation (human vs. LLM) is a critical factor that can alter energy consumption.

Furthermore, our work extends Georgiou et al.'s analysis by including memory usage and comparing algorithm implementations generated by large language models (LLMs) with their human-written counterparts. Specifically, we evaluate LLM-generated and human-authored implementations from two distinct code repositories. Another key difference is that, unlike previous studies, we do not categorize programming languages by execution paradigm; instead, we focus solely on comparing their energy efficiency, memory consumption, and execution time.

3 Study Design

We conduct our study in two phases. In the first phase, we evaluate the correctness, energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time of code generated by Large Language Models (LLMs) accessed via the Groq API [GroqCloud 2025]. In the second phase, we analyze these same aspects in the context of LLM-based code assistant applications (e.g., ChatGPT [OpenAI 2024]). The former allows us to obtain results that, free of any user context, can be reproduced by other researchers. Conversely, the latter brings results regarding the actual usage of a user of such applications.

In the remainder of this section, we explain our research questions in Section 3.1. We also detail our goal, metrics, measurement procedure and setup, and data evaluation in Section 3.2.

3.1 Research Questions

In this study, we aim to evaluate the implementation of algorithms generated by large language models (LLMs), accessed via the Groq API [GroqCloud 2025] and LLM-based code assistant applications, in terms of correctness, energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time across different programming languages. To guide our investigation, we define the following four research questions:

- **RQ1**- Are algorithm implementations generated by Large Language Models correct?
- **RQ2**- How energy-efficient are algorithm implementations generated by Large Language Models?
- **RQ3**- How memory-efficient are algorithm implementations generated by Large Language Models?
- **RQ4**- How time-efficient are algorithm implementations generated by Large Language Models?

Although our research questions use the general term Large Language Models (LLMs), we specifically refer to both LLMs accessed via the Groq API (e.g., deepseek-r1-distill-llama-70b) and LLM-based code assistant applications (e.g., ChatGPT). In Section 4, we present a separate assessment for each.

The first research question (**RQ1**) investigates whether algorithm implementations generated by LLMs are both syntactically and semantically correct. This question is crucial, as the correctness of such algorithm implementations directly impacts the reliability of software systems that incorporate them. Understanding how often these implementations compile successfully and produce the expected output can help developers assess when LLMs are a viable option for their projects.

In parallel with **RQ1**, we introduce **RQ2**, which seeks to assess the energy efficiency of algorithm implementations generated by various LLMs. This inquiry is driven by the principles of Green Computing [Paul et al. 2023, Guldner et al. 2024, Kern et al. 2018], emphasizing the significance of energy-efficient software. By analyzing the energy consumption of these algorithm implementations, we can determine the extent to which these tools align with sustainable development goals in computing practices.

Moreover, we introduce **RQ3**, which aims to determine whether algorithm implementations generated by LLMs have comparable memory requirements. This question is motivated by the need to optimize system performance, as memory consumption plays a critical role in the execution of applications, particularly in resource-constrained environments [Pereira et al. 2017]. Understanding differences in memory consumption can help developers assess the suitability of these algorithm implementations for memory-sensitive applications [Pereira et al. 2017].

Lastly, **RQ4** addresses whether the execution times of algorithm implementations generated by different assistants are consistent. The execution time is crucial in determining the performance and efficiency of the algorithm implementation, particularly for real-time or performance-critical applications. Understanding variations in execution time across different LLMs can help select the most suitable approach for time-sensitive tasks [Paul et al. 2023].

3.2 Research Methodology

In this work, we adopt the Green Software Measurement Model [Guldner et al. 2024], a framework composed of five key components that allows us to organize our research methodology. We detail how we use each one in the following.

A- Measured object and goals. Our measured object is threefold. First, we select five LLMs: deepseek-r1-distill-llama-70b, gemma2-9b-it, llama-3.2-90b-vision-preview, llama-3.3-70b-versatile, and mixtral-8x7b-32768 [GroqCloud 2025]. We select these models because, as of March 2025, they are among the most advanced freely available LLMs on the GroqCloud [GroqCloud 2025]. Additionally, we select six LLM-based code assistant applications: AmazonQ [AWS 2024], Blackbox [BlackBox AI 2024], ChatGPT [OpenAI 2024], Codeium [Hunts.AI 2024], Gemini [Google 2024], and Copilot [GitHub 2024]. We base this selection on their recognition in both the market and academic research [Corso et al. 2024b]. Additionally, these applications include chat functionality, allowing for direct interaction during code generation.

Second, we utilize two code repositories as control groups: Rosetta Code [Rosetta Code 2025] and The Algorithms [The Algorithms 2025]. The former stands out as a platform designed for solving computational problems across various programming languages, making it suitable for comparative analysis. Additionally, the latter is an open-source code library that offers algorithm implementations in multiple languages, serving as a resource for educational and research purposes.

Third, we select a set of ten algorithms for our study: Dijkstra (Shortest Path algorithm), AVL Tree (insertion operation), Heap Sort, Bubble Sort, Merge Sort, Quick Sort (non-recursive), Queue, Bead Sort, Bogo Sort, and Binary Search. We select these algorithms as our initial sample due to the authors' familiarity with them and their popularity.

Additionally, the implementations of these algorithms are available in both The Rosetta Code [Rosetta Code 2025] and The Algorithms [The Algorithms 2025], which allow us to make comparisons between generated and human-written code. In this work, our sample consists of these algorithms in Java, Python, and C. We plan to consider other popular languages in future work.

Lastly, our research aims to investigate the impact of algorithm implementations generated by LLM accessed via the Groq API and LLM-based code assistant applications on four key aspects: correctness, energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time. In this context, such analysis seeks to determine whether code generated by LLM is suitable in these areas compared to human-written code. Also, our goal is to perform such an investigation from the perspective of a typical user prompting these tools.

B- Measurement and metrics. In summary, for this study, we select the metrics: Percentage of Functional Correctness (PFC), Energy Consumption in Joules, Memory Consumption in Megabytes, and Execution Time in Milliseconds.

First, functional correctness is important for evaluating the functional accuracy of generated code [Corso et al. 2024b]. Therefore, our goal is to assess whether various LLMs can produce reliable and useful algorithm implementations. To achieve this goal, we assess correctness using the percentage of algorithm implementations that are both syntactically and semantically correct as the primary metric [Corso et al. 2024b]. Algorithm implementations are categorized into four distinct groups: (1) Correct: both syntactically and semantically accurate, (2) Plausible: minor syntactic error, but semantically accurate, (3) Incorrect: semantically wrong, and (4) Invalid: fails to compile or produces unexpected output. This classification provides a structured approach to assessing the quality and applicability of generated algorithm implementations. In this context, to support answering **RQ1**, we adopt the Percentage of Functional Correctness (PFC) metric [Corso et al. 2024b], which quantifies the proportion of correct and plausible implementations relative to the total number of implementations.

Additionally, energy consumption is an increasing concern for computer manufacturers, software language designers, programmers, and even everyday users [Pereira et al. 2017]. This issue is particularly critical for battery-powered devices, where lower energy usage extends battery life and reduces the need for frequent recharging [Hindle et al. 2014]. While the initial emphasis on energy efficiency came from hardware manufacturers, it has now extended to software developers as well [Pinto et al. 2014].

As outlined in Section 3.1, **RQ2** focuses on energy consumption. To address this question, we use the Joule (J) as the unit of measurement to quantify the energy consumed during algorithm execution. This metric allows for a direct comparison of the energy efficiency between LLM-generated algorithm implementations and their human-written counterparts. By evaluating energy usage in this way, we aim to determine whether LLMs are capable of producing energy-efficient code.

Another measurement we consider in this study is memory consumption, as it can establish how efficiently the generated algorithm implementations manage memory usage. Understanding memory consumption could be valuable for developers in a broader context, as it could help them optimize resource use, maintain system stability, and prevent memory exhaustion [Drepper 2007]. In this context, we measure memory consumption in Megabytes (MB) during algorithm execution, capturing the peak memory usage of the algorithm's process. This approach provides an assessment of how different LLM-generated algorithm implementations perform with regard to memory consumption. With these results, we aim to address **RQ3**.

Moreover, execution time directly reflects the performance of the algorithm implementations. Thus, we include this measurement to demonstrate how a given algorithm

implementation performs when its code is generated by different LLMs. In this way, we measure execution time in milliseconds (MS). For that purpose, we record the start and end times of algorithm execution. The time difference, calculated in MS, provides a quantitative measure of how quickly each algorithm executes. This allows for a comparison of performance across LLM-generated algorithm implementations. To sum up, we use the millisecond rates to answer **RQ4**.

Lastly, prior work employs the same correctness measure as we do [Corso et al. 2024b]. Other previous work also highlights Joules as a natural measure for energy consumption, Megabytes for memory consumption, or Milliseconds for execution time [Guldner et al. 2024, Pereira et al. 2017, Georgiou et al. 2017, Hindle et al. 2014, Pereira et al. 2021].

C- Measurement procedure models. Initially, we assess correctness by analyzing the compilation and execution of each algorithm once, following the methodology described by Corso et al. [Corso et al. 2024b]. We then create a table showing the distribution of algorithm implementations in the correctness categories (correct, plausible, incorrect, and invalid) for each generated algorithm implementation. Afterwards, we determine the percentage for each category by calculating the ratio of algorithm implementations classified in that category to the total number produced by the respective LLM.

Moreover, we adapt a script provided by Couto et al. [Couto et al. 2017a] to run each algorithm 1,000 times to measure energy consumption and execution time. This script records the power consumption after each execution and specifically uses the `gettimeofday` function² to capture the start and end times of the algorithm execution. It takes the difference between the values, resulting in the execution time in milliseconds. In summary, this script's output consists of measures of energy consumption in Joules and execution time in milliseconds for each algorithm implementation.

To measure memory consumption, we navigate the directory containing the algorithm implementation and execute the `make mem` command within a Makefile, which runs the target algorithm implementation with the `time -v`³ command. This command provides a detailed analysis of the resource usage for the specified number of iterations (in this case, 1,000 times). Specifically, we record the "Maximum resident set size (kbytes)" which indicates the peak memory usage in kilobytes.

D- Measurement setup. In this study, we use RAPL (Running Average Power Limit) [David et al. 2010, Intel 2024], an Intel technology that enables real-time measurement and control of energy consumption in hardware components. It operates by monitoring the voltage and current within the processor, making it possible to measure energy usage for the CPU, DRAM, and other supported components. Additionally, RAPL allows us to limit energy consumption based on configurable values, ensuring that measurements remain precise and within acceptable standards. This tool proves particularly useful in energy efficiency experiments, as it directly analyzes the impact of software on the hardware [Pereira et al. 2021].

To use the RAPL tool, we adapt a script⁴ from the work of Pereira et al. [Pereira et al. 2017] that provides the result of the energy and time spent by a specific process. The program initially receives three input arguments: the command for the process to execute, the language or description (which we use to name the output CSV file), and the name of the test, serving as an identifier for the data we collect. In each execution,

² <https://www.man7.org/linux/man-pages/man2/gettimeofday.2.html>

³ <https://www.man7.org/linux/man-pages/man1/time.1.html>

⁴ <https://tinyurl.com/greensoftwarelab>

the program generates a CSV file with the name of the test, the energy consumption information that we record through the `rapl_before` and `rapl_after` functions, and the execution time, which is, by default, repeated over 1,000 times.

To evaluate the selected LLMs and LLM-based code assistants, we use a simple prompt reflecting typical usage: “Please write your best implementation of [algorithm name] in [programming language]”. The placeholders are replaced with the specific algorithm and programming language needed. While we are aware of various prompting techniques [Wei et al. 2022, Kojima et al. 2022, Yao et al. 2023, Shinn et al. 2023], our goal is to test the models in a way a typical user would interact with them [Marvin et al. 2024]. For this reason, we do not employ advanced prompting methods in this study. However, in future work, we plan to investigate how different prompting techniques might influence the results.

For the selected models in GroqCloud (`deepseek-r1-distill-llama-70b`, `gemma2-9b-it`, `llama-3.2-90b-vision-preview`, `llama-3.3-70b-versatile`, and `mixtral-8x7b-32768`), we include the given prompt in an API call, as shown in line 4 of Listing 1. This prompt requests an implementation of Dijkstra’s algorithm in Python.

In line 3, we set the role to “user”, ensuring the request is processed as user input. The model selection occurs in line 6, where we specify `deepseek-r1-distill-llama-70b`, and in line 7, we set the temperature to zero. By using a temperature of zero, we enforce determinism, meaning the model always generates the same response for a given prompt. This approach eliminates variability caused by user context or conversation history.

```

1 chat_completion = client.chat.completions.create(
2   messages=[{
3     "role": "user",
4     "content": "Please write your best implementation of Dijkstra
                    algorithm in Python programming language.",
5   }],
6   model="deepseek-r1-distill-llama-70b",
7   temperature = 0
8 )
9 print(chat_completion.choices[0].message.content)

```

Listing 1: Example of a Groq API call

For the set of applications (AmazonQ, Blackbox, ChatGPT, Codeium, Gemini, and GitHub Copilot), we input the aforementioned prompt into their respective chat interfaces. This approach captures results from a user’s perspective in a non-deterministic manner.

At last, to run our experiments, we use a desktop computer with an Intel Core i3 processor, 8 GB of RAM, and the Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS operating system due to its compatibility with RAPL [David et al. 2010, Intel 2024].

E- Data evaluation models. To analyze correctness, we define a script to automate the compilation process, allowing us to identify which algorithm implementations compile correctly. Therefore, it automatically tries to compile the LLM-generated algorithm implementations and their human-written counterparts. This solution checks directories recursively for Makefile files, enabling it to execute commands such as `compile`, `run`, `clean`, `mem`, and `measure`. When it finds a Makefile, the script executes the corresponding command and provides feedback on any errors that occur during compilation or execution. It utilizes the `subprocess` module⁵ to run shell commands, managing the output and errors.

With the script’s output, we record the correctness metric in a table that includes the percentage of correct, plausible, incorrect, and invalid entries for each generated algorithm

⁵ <https://docs.python.org/3/library/subprocess.html>

implementation. Additionally, we register the data concerning energy consumption, memory consumption, and execution time in a spreadsheet for further analysis.

Next, we calculate the mean over 1,000 executions of each algorithm implementation to generate our report. Based on these results, we create spreadsheets that present energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time. Each spreadsheet focuses on a specific metric, enabling comparative analysis across implementations. We also use this data to generate tables and visualizations, aiming to facilitate the interpretation of differences between LLM-generated and human-written algorithm implementations.

Last but not least, we provide all our research material in our Online Appendix [Online Appendix 2025].

4 Results

In this section, we present our research findings and address each research question in detail. We discuss whether algorithm implementations generated by LLMs are semantically and syntactically correct in Section 4.1. Moreover, we discuss our results regarding the energy, memory, and time efficiency of these implementations in Sections 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4, respectively. Lastly, we discuss our results in Section 4.5 and detail the threats to validity regarding our study in Section 4.6.

4.1 Correctness

This section presents our results on correctness regarding **RQ1**. First, we explain the findings for the LLMs accessed via Groq API calls, namely deepseek-r1-distill-llama-70b, gemma2-9b-it, llama-3.2-90b-vision-preview, and llama-3.3-70b-versatile. Second, we cover the results for the selected LLM-Based Code Assistant applications, including AmazonQ, Blackbox, ChatGPT, Codeium, Gemini, and GitHub Copilot. This structure is maintained throughout the following sections. Since all the algorithm implementations in our sample from Rosetta and The Algorithms are classified as *Correct*, we exclude them from further analysis for the sake of simplicity. As stated in Section 3.2, we use the Percentage of Functional Correctness (PFC), which represents the sum of *Correct* and *Plausible* implementations [Corso et al. 2024b].

Groq API. Table 1 presents the correctness results for the five selected LLMs accessed via the Groq API, evaluated across Java, Python, and C programming languages. The gemma2-9b-it model (**gemma2**) achieves a 100% PFC rate for both Java and Python. In other words, this LLM produced 18 *Correct* implementations and two *Plausible* ones out of 20 attempts. Both *Plausible* outputs were caused by missing import statements. However, we classify one C-generated implementation as *Invalid* due to a compilation error. As shown in Listing 2, **gemma2** attempts to implement the BogoSort algorithm but fails to declare the variable `i` used in line 5, resulting in the error.

LLMs	gemma2			deepseek			llama33			llama32			mixtral		
Language	Java	Python	C	Java	Python	C	Java	Python	C	Java	Python	C	Java	Python	C
<i>Correct</i>	9	9	9	8	9	9	10	10	10	10	10	10	8	-	9
<i>Plausible</i>	1	1	-	2	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-
<i>Incorrect</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
<i>Invalid</i>	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PFC	100	100	90	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	-	90

Table 1: Correctness results of LLMs accessed by Groq API across programming languages.

```

1 void bogoSort(int arr[], int n) {
2   srand(time(NULL));
3   while (1) {
4     for (...) {...}
5     if (i == n - 1) { break; } ... }

```

Listing 2: Invalid BogoSort implementation by gemma2 in C

Furthermore, the deepseek-r1-distill-llama-70b model (**deepseek**) also presents *Plausible* occurrences. In this way, we make minor changes in four out of 30 generated implementations. For example, the structure and logic of an AVL Tree implementation in Python are correct; however, it lacks a null check for a rotation procedure, resulting in a runtime error. We fix this issue by adding a null check to prevent such an error.

Interestingly, both the llama-3.3-70b-versatile and llama-3.2-90b-vision-preview models (**llama33** and **llama32**, respectively) achieve a 100% PFC rate. Specifically, 30 out of 30 generated algorithm implementations are classified as *Correct*. In contrast, the mixtral-8x7b-32768 model (**mixtral**) presents ten *Correct* results for Java and one *Incorrect* implementation for C. This *Incorrect* implementation also regards the Bogo Sort algorithm. This code compiles and runs without signaling errors, but it fails semantically. Instead of implementing a random sorting strategy as expected in Bogo Sort, **mixtral** produces a Bubble Sort.

Last but not least, as shown in Table 1, we do not report results for **mixtral** in Python. Unfortunately, the Groq API stopped providing access to this model during our experiments. As a result, we were only able to collect results for Java and C, which we executed first.

Applications. Table 2 presents the correctness results for the selected LLM-based applications. Notably, **BlackBox**, **Copilot**, and **Gemini** achieve 30 *Correct* implementations out of 30, corresponding to a 100% PFC rate. In contrast, **AmazonQ**, **Codeium**, and **ChatGPT** attain PFC rates of 70%, 90%, and 90%, respectively.

Applications	AmazonQ			BlackBox			Codeium			Copilot			ChatGPT			Gemini		
	Java	Python	C	Java	Python	C	Java	Python	C	Java	Python	C	Java	Python	C	Java	Python	C
<i>Correct</i>	7	10	10	10	10	10	10	9	10	10	10	10	10	9	10	10	10	10
<i>Plausible</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Incorrect</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Invalid</i>	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-
PFC	70	100	100	100	100	100	100	90	100	100	100	100	100	90	100	100	100	100

Table 2: Correctness results for LLM-Based Code Assistant applications across programming languages.

First, the 70% PFC rate of **AmazonQ** for Java occurs due to three *Invalid* implementations. Specifically, this application mistakenly provides code for the AVL Tree, Dijkstra’s algorithm, and Merge Sort algorithms in Java. Listing 3 shows the generation of an AVL Tree algorithm in Java that lacks essential procedures for node removal and re-balancing. Interestingly, it stops the code generation and prints the message ”Sorry, I cannot answer that question” and thus could not properly answer our prompt.

```

1 private Node remove(Node node, int key) {
2   if (node == null) return null;
3   updateHeights(node);
4   int balance = getBalance(node);
5   if (balance > 1 || balance < -1) { Sorry, I cannot answer that question

```

Listing 3: Invalid AVL Tree implementation by AmazonQ in Java

Second, **Codeium** and **ChatGPT** achieve a 90% rate for Python. Indeed, we classify one algorithm implementation as *Invalid* due to a runtime error. Coincidentally, this occurs for the Bead Sort implementation, where incorrect index manipulation within an auxiliary array leads to an `IndexError`. In particular, the **ChatGPT** Bead Sort implementation constructs a 2D matrix with variable row lengths and subsequently attempts to sum over the columns without verifying uniform dimensions. This results in an out-of-bounds list access.

Answering the research question. We address **RQ1** by confirming that both the LLMs accessed via the Groq API and the LLM-based code assistant applications are capable of generating correct algorithm implementations. The former achieves an average PFC rate of 98.57%, while the latter reaches an average of 97.22%. This result confirms our expectation, as we initially hypothesized that the Groq API would yield higher rates due to the absence of context bias—even though the underlying LLMs differ. We further discuss it in Section 4.5.

4.2 Energy Efficiency

In this section, we present the results related to **RQ2**, focusing on the energy efficiency of algorithm implementations generated by LLMs accessed through the Groq API and by LLM-based code assistant applications. For both, we evaluate the energy consumption of each generated algorithm implementation across different programming languages in Joules, as outlined in Section 3.2. Table 3 presents the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum energy consumption (in Joules) for the execution of the selected algorithms provided by **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** across Java, Python, and C.

Groq API. Table 4 presents the energy consumption results for each LLM. In this context, **deepseek** exhibits the highest average energy consumption for Java-generated algorithm implementations (1.6504), along with a low standard deviation (0.0911). Additionally, it records both the highest minimum and maximum energy consumption values among the evaluated models. In contrast, **gemma2** demonstrates the lowest average energy consumption for Java-generated algorithm implementations. Notably, **gemma2** outperforms even the human-written implementations from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** in terms of energy efficiency (Table 3).

Repository	Lang.	Mean	Median	S. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Rosetta Code	Java	1.3403	1.2755	0.1068	1.2524	1.6484
	Python	2.0029	0.5726	3.1988	0.0444	10.3247
	C	0.6582	0.0583	0.8771	0.0345	2.2715
The Algorithms	Java	1.3226	1.2656	0.1227	1.2486	1.6359
	Python	1.5915	0.7574	2.8894	0.0541	9.5357
	C	0.5675	0.0530	0.7492	0.0276	1.9829

Table 3: Energy results of human-written implementation across programming languages.

Moreover, **gemma2** exhibits the lowest average energy consumption for Python-generated algorithm implementations (1.0201 Joules). However, it also shows a high standard deviation (1.6107), primarily due to significant variability between specific algorithm executions. For instance, the execution of Bubble Sort consumes 5.3786 Joules—the highest recorded value—while Bogo Sort consumes only 0.0712 Joules, the

lowest. Notably, the Bubble Sort implementations generated by **gemma2**, **deepseek**, **llama32**, and **llama33** all consume more than 5 Joules. In contrast, the same algorithm implementation provided by **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** consumes less than 1 Joule.

Nonetheless, when considering the average energy consumption across all algorithm implementations, **Rosetta** exhibits the highest value at 2.0029 Joules. This is primarily due to its Bead Sort implementation, which consumes 10.3247 Joules—the highest among all measured executions. A similar situation occurs with **The Algorithms**, where Bead Sort reaches a peak consumption of 9.5357 Joules. However, as shown in Table 3, the median energy consumption for **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** is substantially lower: 0.5726 and 0.7574 Joules, respectively. Excluding Bead Sort, both repositories emerge as the most energy-efficient overall. In other words, human-written implementations outperform LLM-generated ones for Python algorithm implementations when we disregard outliers such as Bead Sort.

The **Gemma2** LLM also achieves the lowest average energy consumption for algorithm implementations generated by C, at 0.0390 Joules. In fact, the five evaluated LLMs demonstrate lower energy consumption for C implementations compared to the human-written counterparts from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms**.

LLM	Lang.	Mean	Median	S. Dev.	Min.	Max.
deepseek	Java	1.6504	1.6676	0.0911	1.5551	1.8727
	Python	1.3517	0.8458	1.8321	0.0737	5.9897
	C	0.1205	0.0491	0.2183	0.0268	0.6761
gemma2	Java	1.3057	1.2515	0.1309	1.2388	1.6276
	Python	1.0201	0.6351	1.6107	0.0712	5.3786
	C	0.0390	0.0383	0.0266	0.0255	0.1093
llama32	Java	1.3733	1.2798	0.1488	1.2635	1.6221
	Python	1.1400	0.7740	1.7255	0.0839	5.9124
	C	0.4097	0.0463	0.6594	0.0244	2.0868
llama33	Java	1.6331	1.6649	0.1208	1.3334	1.7208
	Python	1.5398	0.7159	1.8053	0.0739	6.0109
	C	0.2980	0.0462	0.5661	0.0237	1.7742
mixtral	Java	1.6112	1.6478	0.1126	1.3775	1.6981
	Python	-	-	-	-	-
	C	0.4253	0.0522	0.7018	0.0388	2.1031

Table 4: Energy results of LLMs accessed by Groq API across programming languages.

Applications. Table 5 presents the energy consumption results for the LLM-based code assistant applications. In this context, **Copilot** exhibits the highest average and median energy consumption for Java-generated algorithm implementations, at 1.5582 and 1.6617 Joules, respectively. It also records the highest maximum (1.6721) and minimum (1.2860) values, primarily due to the high energy usage observed in the Bead Sort, Binary Search, Heap Sort, and Merge Sort algorithm implementations. In contrast, **Codeium** achieves the lowest average (1.2869) and standard deviation (0.1024), outperforming the human-written implementations from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** in terms of energy efficiency for Java.

Surprisingly, **AmazonQ** exhibits the highest average energy consumption for Python-generated algorithm implementations, reaching 4.1725 Joules—more than twice the average of the second highest, **Copilot**. It also shows a high standard deviation of 10.3131 Joules, primarily driven by the exceptionally high energy usage of the Bead Sort execution, which consumes 33.1024 Joules—the highest value recorded in our study. Although **BlackBox**, **Copilot**, and **Gemini** also generate Bead Sort implementations

with high energy consumption (all exceeding 7 Joules), they still perform better than the human-written versions from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms**, which each exceed 9 Joules.

In contrast to **AmazonQ**, **Codeium** achieves the lowest recorded energy consumption for Python-generated algorithm implementations, with an average of 0.3822 Joules. Its energy efficiency is further reflected in its maximum consumption value—just 0.8065 Joules during the execution of Binary Search. Therefore, **Codeium** outperforms the human-written implementations from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** in terms of energy efficiency.

Finally, we observe that LLM-based code assistant applications also outperform human-written implementations in terms of energy efficiency for C-generated algorithm implementations. Among them, **Copilot** achieves the lowest average energy consumption, at 0.2682 Joules, while **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** register higher averages of 0.6582 and 0.5675 Joules, respectively.

App.	Lang.	Mean	Median	S. Dev.	Min.	Max.
AmazonQ	Java	1.3306	1.2694	0.1394	1.2403	1.6431
	Python	4.1725	0.7403	10.3131	0.0531	33.1024
	C	0.2755	0.0623	0.4294	0.0303	1.2194
BlackBox	Java	1.3309	1.2892	0.1364	1.2393	1.6663
	Python	0.6382	0.6667	0.6638	0.0717	2.3068
	C	0.3497	0.0503	0.7707	0.0255	2.4867
Codeium	Java	1.2869	1.2668	0.1024	1.2605	1.6060
	Python	0.3822	0.3814	0.2785	0.0517	0.8065
	C	0.3355	0.0561	0.6469	0.0292	2.0841
Copilot	Java	1.5582	1.6617	0.1483	1.2860	1.6721
	Python	1.6370	0.6506	3.6781	0.0557	11.9581
	C	0.2682	0.0623	0.4138	0.0228	1.2241
ChatGPT	Java	1.5146	1.6374	0.1608	1.2463	1.6718
	Python	0.4763	0.6900	0.3485	0.0574	0.8332
	C	0.3169	0.0475	0.5256	0.0233	1.6208
Gemini	Java	1.3555	1.2836	0.1314	1.2618	1.6311
	Python	1.0981	0.5714	2.2818	0.0557	7.5210
	C	1.3589	0.0564	3.8591	0.0230	12.3622

Table 5: Energy results for LLM-based code assistant applications across programming languages.

Answering the research question. In response to **RQ2**, our findings indicate that algorithm implementations generated by LLMs are generally more energy-efficient than human-written implementations. However, this efficiency varies depending on the programming language and the specific algorithm. Among the LLMs accessed via the Groq API, **gemma2** demonstrates the best energy performance across Java, Python, and C. In addition, for LLM-based code assistant applications, **Codeium** stands out as the most energy-efficient option for Java and Python, while **Copilot** performs best for C.

4.3 Memory Efficiency

This section presents the results related to **RQ3**, focusing on the memory efficiency of algorithm implementations generated by LLMs accessed via the Groq API and by LLM-based code assistant applications. Additionally, we compare these results with human-written implementations from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms**. Table 6 summarizes the memory consumption in megabytes across Java, Python, and C.

Groq API. Table 7 summarizes the memory consumption (in megabytes) for each LLM, reporting the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values across Java, Python, and C. In this context, **llama33** achieves the lowest average memory consumption for Java at 38.2916 MB. Although this result is more efficient than the averages observed for both **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** (see Table 6), **llama33** also registers the highest maximum value—53.200 MB—due to its implementation of Dijkstra’s algorithm in Java, which is the most memory-consuming among all LLMs and human-written repositories. In contrast, **mixtral** records the highest average memory consumption for Java implementations among the LLMs, yet still remains below that of **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms**.

In contrast to the previous results, human-written algorithm implementations present good results in terms of memory efficiency for Python-generated implementations. As shown in Table 6, implementations from **The Algorithms** exhibit an average memory consumption of 12.5313 megabytes, which is lower than the 15.1424 megabytes recorded by **llama33** (Table 7), the most efficient among the evaluated LLMs. These findings indicate that, for Python, human-written algorithm implementations are more memory efficient than those generated by LLMs.

Repository	Lang.	Mean	Median	S. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Rosetta Code	Java	40.6680	40.9500	2.1284	35.9560	43.6240
	Python	17.7560	10.5640	12.4944	10.4480	48.5120
	C	4.3652	1.3680	6.5957	1.2600	21.7200
The Algorithms	Java	40.4627	39.2480	2.1065	37.8280	43.6440
	Python	12.5313	10.6760	4.1174	10.3760	22.7200
	C	2.7988	1.3480	3.4078	1.2520	11.0120

Table 6: Memory results for human-written implementation across programming languages.

Notably, we observe high maximum memory consumption values for **deepseek**, **gemma2**, and **llama32**, reaching 109.3480, 109.3600, and 109.2720 megabytes, respectively. These peaks are all associated with the execution of Dijkstra’s algorithm. The elevated consumption occurs because these implementations rely on Python’s `heapq`⁶ library, which is not optimized for handling large graphs. In our experiments, we use a graph with 1,000 nodes for all memory measurements.

Last but not least, **gemma2** achieves the lowest average memory consumption for C-generated algorithm implementations, at 1.870 megabytes. Interestingly, all five LLMs evaluated outperform the human-written implementations from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** in this context. These results suggest that, for the C language, LLM-generated algorithm implementations tend to be more memory-efficient than their human-written counterparts.

Applications. Table 8 presents the memory consumption results for LLM-based code assistant applications. **Blackbox** achieves the lowest average memory consumption for Java-generated algorithm implementations, at 39.732 megabytes. Notably, it is the only application that outperforms the human-written implementations from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** (as shown in Table 6). This contrasts with the results observed for the Groq API LLMs (Table 7), where all evaluated models consumed less memory than their human-written counterparts.

⁶ <https://docs.python.org/3/library/heapq.html>

LLM	Lang.	Mean	Median	S. Dev.	Min.	Max.
deepseek	Java	38.7730	39.1520	1.9456	35.4160	40.9920
	Python	20.3852	10.4640	31.3149	10.1400	109.3480
	C	1.2040	1.1520	0.0791	1.1520	1.3560
gemma2	Java	38.6898	37.6160	2.1971	36.4000	41.9560
	Python	20.3212	10.4000	31.3194	10.1320	109.3600
	C	1.0870	1.0240	0.1023	1.0240	1.2800
llama32	Java	39.2215	37.3120	9.1671	17.7960	51.2430
	Python	22.6784	10.5200	30.9841	10.2760	109.2720
	C	1.5512	1.1520	1.1764	1.0240	4.8640
llama33	Java	38.2916	37.5140	6.9267	27.5080	53.2000
	Python	15.1424	10.4680	14.9135	10.1400	57.0880
	C	1.5212	1.1520	1.2454	1.0240	4.9920
mixtral	Java	39.7836	39.1240	2.5693	37.1440	46.0920
	Python	-	-	-	-	-
	C	1.0947	1.0240	0.1018	1.0240	1.2800

Table 7: Memory results for LLM accessed by Groq API across programming languages.

App.	Lang.	Mean	Median	S. Dev.	Min.	Max.
AmazonQ	Java	40.883	41.096	1.867	39.188	43.488
	Python	11.182	10.648	1.311	10.184	13.892
	C	1.452	1.360	0.247	1.296	2.016
BlackBox	Java	39.732	39.680	1.030	30.652	41.452
	Python	10.627	10.552	0.397	10.180	11.352
	C	1.294	1.316	0.107	1.128	1.492
Codeium	Java	41.068	41.056	2.368	35.884	43.728
	Python	10.739	10.724	0.017	10.520	11.012
	C	1.280	1.240	0.116	1.172	1.496
Copilot	Java	40.914	41.088	1.553	39.276	43.528
	Python	11.250	10.556	2.137	10.324	17.252
	C	1.743	1.328	1.246	1.240	5.244
ChatGPT	Java	40.949	41.008	1.774	39.188	43.264
	Python	10.887	10.612	0.633	10.064	11.884
	C	1.748	1.352	1.230	1.192	5.136
Gemini	Java	40.823	40.848	1.698	39.056	43.324
	Python	11.491	10.572	2.049	10.272	17.124
	C	1.580	1.240	1.249	1.116	5.124

Table 8: Memory results for LLM-based code assistant applications across programming languages.

Unlike the results observed for Java, Python-generated algorithm implementations consume less memory than their human-written counterparts. In particular, **BlackBox** achieves the lowest average memory usage, at 10.627 megabytes. Similarly, for C-generated algorithm implementations, LLM-based applications also outperform the implementations from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms**. In this case, **Codeium** stands out with the lowest average memory consumption at 1.280 megabytes.

Answering the research question. Regarding **RQ3**, our findings indicate that algorithm implementations generated by LLMs are not always more memory-efficient than human-written implementations. Among the LLMs accessed via the Groq API, **llama33** achieves the lowest average memory consumption for Java. In contrast, implementations from **The Algorithms** are more efficient for Python, while **gemma2** presents the lowest memory usage for C. Additionally, among the LLM-based code assistant applications, only **BlackBox** surpasses human-written implementations in memory efficiency for

Java. However, for Python and C, assistant applications outperform their human-written counterparts in terms of memory consumption.

4.4 Time Efficiency

This section presents the results related to **RQ4**, which focuses on the time efficiency of the algorithm implementations generated by LLMs accessed via the Groq API and by LLM-based code assistant applications. Table 9 shows the results for the execution time mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum in milliseconds for the Rosetta and The Algorithms repositories.

Groq API. Table 10 presents the execution time results for the LLMs accessed via the Groq API. In this context, all five evaluated models exhibit higher average execution times for Java-generated algorithm implementations compared to the human-written implementations from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms**. Although **deepseek** produces the fastest algorithm implementations among the LLMs, with an average execution time of 68.8635 milliseconds, it still lags slightly behind **Rosetta** (68.8020 ms) and **The Algorithms** (68.2446 ms).

Repository	Lang.	Mean	Median	S. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Rosetta Code	Java	68.8020	68.4715	1.2135	67.2465	70.0000
	Python	78.8924	21.9965	112.4493	3.5870	343.8990
	C	33.8599	2.1675	43.3068	1.5020	125.5350
The Algorithms	Java	68.2446	68.0655	0.8152	67.3175	70.0000
	Python	65.9084	25.8810	105.7908	3.8660	316.5585
	C	28.7741	2.2000	41.5673	1.4430	125.9135

Table 9: Time results for human-written implementation across programming languages.

In contrast, for Python-generated algorithm implementations, all five models outperform the human-written implementations. For instance, **gemma2**, the fastest among the LLMs, achieves an average execution time of 37.6724 milliseconds, while **The Algorithms** records 65.9084 milliseconds. Notably, both the LLMs and the human-written repositories exhibit high maximum values. This is primarily due to the execution of Bubble Sort among the LLMs and the execution of Bead Sort in **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms**.

Moreover, we observe a similar pattern for C-generated algorithm implementations, in which LLMs outperform the human-written implementations. Notably, **gemma2** and **deepseek** generate algorithm implementations that are, on average, at least five times faster than their human-written counterparts. For example, **gemma2** achieves an average execution time of just 1.8721 milliseconds, compared to 28.7741 milliseconds for **The Algorithms**.

Applications. Table 11 presents the execution time results for the LLM-based assistant applications. For Java-generated algorithm implementations, the results follow a similar pattern to those observed for the Groq API LLMs: the human-written implementations from **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms** are faster than the algorithm implementations generated by the assistant applications. **BlackBox** achieves the best result among the assistant applications, with an average execution time of 68.3909 milliseconds. However, it remains slightly slower than **The Algorithms**, which records 68.2446 milliseconds (Table 9).

LLM	Lang.	Mean	Median	S. Dev.	Min.	Max.
deepseek	Java	68.8635	68.1160	3.2979	63.5700	76.6960
	Python	43.8558	26.7570	62.5254	5.5000	199.2435
	C	5.6791	1.7680	9.0770	1.4870	26.7235
gemma2	Java	68.8763	68.5125	1.7158	67.4770	72.5085
	Python	37.6724	25.5875	52.7694	5.0340	181.2905
	C	1.8721	1.6000	0.7722	1.4360	3.8560
llama32	Java	69.2243	68.0345	2.0926	67.1370	73.0000
	Python	39.7522	26.6110	58.3929	6.0220	197.3025
	C	22.1102	1.6735	39.4304	1.4055	125.2610
llama33	Java	69.2907	68.3680	2.2998	67.7865	75.0000
	Python	54.3910	26.2890	64.5097	5.5300	200.1625
	C	12.4826	1.7055	22.8407	1.4115	67.1295
mixtral	Java	69.2970	68.6113	1.5596	67.4550	72.1705
	Python	-	-	-	-	-
	C	17.9536	1.8583	38.9980	1.6335	125.8785

Table 10: Time results for LLMs accessed by Groq API across programming languages.

App.	Lang.	Mean	Median	S. Dev.	Min.	Max.
AmazonQ	Java	70.0953	68.3990	5.5754	67.2465	85.0905
	Python	126.8054	24.8940	338.5089	3.6590	1086.2100
	C	9.8967	2.2040	15.5797	1.5075	48.5830
BlackBox	Java	68.3909	67.9390	0.9932	67.1615	69.8175
	Python	24.7832	23.2835	20.9794	5.3910	75.7200
	C	13.7857	2.0090	30.9232	1.4310	100.2485
Codeium	Java	68.4625	68.0825	0.7049	67.7190	69.9655
	Python	17.8877	22.4635	10.9845	3.7260	34.7055
	C	17.7910	2.1000	39.1693	1.4715	125.9795
Copilot	Java	68.5071	67.9343	1.2006	67.1295	70.0985
	Python	55.6044	21.8425	117.5507	4.0700	397.3365
	C	9.7539	1.9175	15.8775	1.3600	43.5285
ChatGPT	Java	69.1058	68.9755	1.4794	67.4680	71.5005
	Python	18.0089	21.8890	10.3794	4.3900	31.5180
	C	12.0195	2.0950	21.3057	1.3780	64.9645
Gemini	Java	69.0615	69.6730	1.0957	67.4150	70.1335
	Python	40.8391	21.5165	75.0566	4.2310	252.7880
	C	84.0679	2.1000	248.9193	1.3630	794.6035

Table 11: Time results for LLM-based code assistant applications across programming languages.

For Python-generated algorithm implementations, the assistant applications generally deliver better performance. For example, **Codeium** achieves an average execution time of 17.8877 milliseconds, significantly outperforming **The Algorithms**, which records 65.9084 milliseconds. Conversely, **AmazonQ** shows the worst performance, with an average execution time of 126.8054 milliseconds and a maximum of 1086.2100 milliseconds—several times higher than those of the other LLMs and repositories. This poor result is primarily due to its implementation of Bead Sort. Specifically, **AmazonQ**'s version iterates from 1 up to the maximum value in the array, and for each iteration, it traverses the entire array, resulting in highly inefficient execution.

Finally, only **Gemini** exhibits a slower average execution time (84.0679 milliseconds) compared to **Rosetta** and **The Algorithms**. Notably, its Bead Sort implementation takes 794.6035 milliseconds to execute for the same reason discussed earlier in the case of **AmazonQ**—it iterates from 1 to the maximum value and, for each iteration, traverses the entire array. In contrast, the other assistant applications achieve faster execution times

than their human-written counterparts.

Answering the research question. In response to **RQ4**, our findings reveal that algorithm implementations generated by LLMs are not always more time-efficient than human-written implementations. Among the models accessed via the Groq API, **The Algorithms** achieve the lowest average execution time for Java, while the LLMs perform better for Python and C. Regarding LLM-based code assistant applications, only **Gemini** delivers worse performance than human-written implementations in terms of execution time for C. However, for Java, human-written implementations remain faster. Finally, for Python, most assistant applications outperform human-written code—except for **AmazonQ**, which presents worse results.

4.5 Discussion

First, the correctness results presented in Section 4.1 suggest that Large Language Models are capable of generating algorithm implementations, such as Bubble Sort and Dijkstra’s Algorithm, correctly. Additionally, we observe only a small difference in correctness between LLMs accessed via the Groq API (98.57%) and LLM-based code assistant applications (97.22%). This finding suggests that user context may have a limited impact on correctness. As discussed in Section 3.2, we configure the Groq API with a temperature of zero to ensure deterministic outputs. In future work, we intend to explore the effects of different temperature settings and evaluate paid models to determine whether PFC rates vary under those conditions.

Moreover, in Sections 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4, we analyze energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time independently. To explore potential relationships between these metrics, we apply the Pearson correlation test [Benesty et al. 2009]. Table 12 shows the coefficients for each possible correlation.

In this context, we observe a strong relationship among energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time when accessing LLMs via the Groq API. However, when analyzing LLM-based code assistant applications, only energy consumption and execution time maintain a strong correlation ($r = 0.85$). In contrast, energy and memory usage, as well as memory and execution time, show weak correlations of 0.22 and 0.03, respectively. These differences suggest that the user context in these applications may influence the observed results. Further investigation is needed to better understand these results, which we plan to explore in future work.

Based on our results, we recommend using the gemma2-9b-it model for the implementation of algorithm generation when low energy consumption is a priority. While this model does not always deliver the best performance in terms of memory usage and execution time, these two metrics are correlated, as discussed above using the Pearson test. Overall, gemma2-9b-it offers the most balanced performance across the evaluated criteria.

Category	Correlation	Coefficient
Groq API	energy and memory	0.87
	energy and time	0.92
	memory and time	0.95
Applications	energy and memory	0.22
	energy and time	0.85
	memory and time	0.03

Table 12: Pearson correlation test

Furthermore, Codeium and Copilot are preferable options when prioritizing low energy consumption, while BlackBox stands out for its low memory usage. In terms of execution time, ChatGPT is the recommended choice. However, we once again emphasize that the user context may have influenced the observed results across these applications.

It is worth noting that our results could be affected by contamination issues, more specifically the **raw text contamination** phenomenon [Sainz et al. 2023]. In other words, models pretrained on web-scale corpora could have been exposed to the same algorithms generated by the LLMs in our evaluations. This could potentially bias the assessment by overestimating the model’s ability to generate syntactically and functionally correct code. Therefore, it becomes essential to verify whether the generated implementations arise from the model’s genuine reasoning capabilities or merely reflect memorized code fragments that may exist in the pretraining corpus.

We further extended this evaluation by applying the *LogProber* algorithm proposed by [Yax et al. 2024], which relates the model’s certainty about the next token (i.e., low log-probability values) to the likelihood that such a sequence has already been encountered during training. Figure 1 presents the cumulative log-probabilities of nine tokens from the *Heapsort* code generated by the Llama-3.2-90B model (green curve) and from a control sequence of tokens certainly present in every LLM’s training corpus (blue curve)⁷.

Figure 1: *LogProber* analysis

The pronounced disparity between the two curves provides evidence that the code generated by the Llama-3.2-90B model was not part of the LLM training set. Markers labeled with ‘o’ indicate that the ground-truth next token was found among the top-20 most probable predictions, whereas markers labeled with ‘x’ denote positions where it was not. In such cases, the log-probability shown corresponds to that of the 20th most probable token, meaning that the green curve still represents an optimistic lower-bound estimate of the model’s uncertainty.

This experiment was conducted using the GPT-4o model (version released on 2024-08-06) since the Groq API does not provide access to token-level log-probabilities. The disparity between the two curves depicted in Figure 1 provides evidence that the code generated by the Llama 3.2 90B model was not part of the GPT-4o training set. Finally, it is unlikely that a code snippet absent from GPT-4o’s corpus would nonetheless appear in the corpus of an open-source LLM such as Llama 3.2.

Last but not least, as demonstrated throughout this section, human-written implementations remain valuable—especially when the focus is on execution time.

⁷ Namely, the initial tokens of the most widely sold book in the western world—the Bible.

4.6 Threats to Validity

In this section, we discuss the potential threats to the validity of our study [Wohlin et al. 2012].

External validity. First, we highlight that our findings pertain specifically to ten algorithms implemented in Java, Python, and C. Consequently, these results cannot be generalized to other programming languages or algorithms. However, it is worth noting that these three languages are among the most widely used by researchers and developers [Statista 2023]. Additionally, our expertise in these languages has enabled us to effectively identify potential errors in source code, inputs, and outputs. In parallel, we draw our conclusions based solely on the selected ten algorithms. Therefore, we cannot generalize our results for other problems. However, the selected algorithms address a variety of problem domains, including sorting, graph processing, and tree manipulation. In future work, we plan to extend our analysis by incorporating additional programming languages and algorithms.

In this work, we evaluate five freely available models in GroqCloud and six LLM-based code assistant applications. The selection of models and applications is intentional, as they represent some of the most popular tools at the time of our experiments [DataCamp 2024]. Similarly, we select the Rosetta Code and The Algorithms repositories as a collection of human-written algorithm implementations [Nanz and Furia 2015, Georgiou et al. 2017, Maier and Felderer 2023, Zhang et al. 2023]. However, results derived from these sources may not extend to other models, applications, or repositories. In fact, many new models and applications have been launched since the execution of our study [GroqCloud 2025, OpenAI 2025, Anthropic 2025]. As future work, we plan to expand this study by incorporating a broader set of models, applications, and repositories.

Moreover, since the RAPL tool is only compatible with Intel processors [David et al. 2010, Pereira et al. 2017], our results may not extend to other setups. For example, using other measuring tools for AMD processors [AMD 2025] could lead to different outcomes. However, RAPL is the state-of-the-art for tools that do not rely on hardware for energy measurements. Additionally, RAPL is widely used for energy consumption measurements in academia for a number of different purposes [Anthony et al. 2020, Gupta et al. 2022, García-Martín et al. 2019, Eckert et al. 2018, Khan et al. 2018, Awad and Khanna 2015, David et al. 2011].

Construct validity. Our research questions focus on well-defined aspects, including correctness, energy consumption, memory usage, and performance. Additionally, the selected metrics (Percentage of Functional Correctness, Joules, Megabytes, and Milliseconds) are straightforward and directly aligned with these aspects. A partial exception is the correctness measure, as we manually classify each algorithm implementation as Correct, Plausible, Incorrect, or Invalid. To mitigate potential biases, we acknowledge the possibility of exploring alternative approaches for assessing correctness [Bui et al. 2025, Liu et al. 2023] in future work.

Internal validity. To measure the Percentage of Functional Correctness (PFC), we follow Corso et al.'s approach [Corso et al. 2024b]. Although such an approach is also followed by other studies [Corso et al. 2024a, Fagadau et al. 2024, Donato et al. 2025, Colombo et al. 2025], it still demands manual work that could introduce bias. To minimize this issue, only one author was responsible for assigning the generated algorithm implementations as Correct, Plausible, Incorrect, or Invalid, while another author was responsible for reviewing the decisions. In this context, we do not find any inconsistencies between the assignment and the review.

To strengthen our results on correctness, we conduct an additional correctness analysis

based on the work of [Khan et al. 2024, Du et al. 2023, Ji et al. 2023], in which we use additional LLMs to analyze the responses of the target models. To do that, we selected five models that are different from those we explain in Section 3: llama-3.1-8b-instant, llama-4-maverick-17b-128e-instruct, kimi-k2-instruct-0905, gpt-oss-120b, and qwen3-32b [GroqCloud 2025]. Table 13 summarizes the results. For instance, according to these five models, **AmazonQ** achieved 34 *Correct* implementations, one *Incorrect* implementation, and 15 *Invalid* implementations⁸.

Models	AmazonQ		BlackBox		Codeium		Copilot		ChatGPT		Gemini		gemma2		deepseek		llama33		llama32		mistral												
	Java	Python	Java	Python	Java	Python	Java	Python	Java	Python	Java	Python	Java	Python	Java	Python	Java	Python	Java	Python	Java	Python											
<i>Correct</i>	34	31	44	32	46	38	43	40	23	35	41	31	36	42	38	36	44	35	32	42	25	36	47	36	42	41	36	46	43	38	38	-	22
<i>Plausible</i>	-	3	4	7	2	5	2	3	13	8	4	9	7	3	9	8	3	7	8	3	5	4	-	5	6	1	4	3	3	6	6	-	8
<i>Incorrect</i>	1	6	2	9	2	6	5	5	12	7	3	6	6	4	2	5	2	8	6	2	14	4	2	6	2	6	9	1	3	6	-	17	
<i>Invalid</i>	15	10	-	2	-	1	-	2	2	-	2	4	1	1	1	1	1	-	4	3	6	6	1	3	-	2	1	-	1	-	-	3	
PFC	68	68	96	78	96	86	90	86	72	86	90	80	86	90	94	88	94	84	80	90	60	80	94	82	96	84	80	98	92	88	88	0	60

Table 13: Correctness results for Debate-based LLM analysis.

Interestingly, the PFC rates vary slightly from those reported in Tables 1 and 2. When the Debate-based approach is used, the PFC rate for the six LLM-based code assistant applications is 12.11% lower. Similarly, for the five LLMs individually, the PFC rate sees a decrease of 7.72%. The differences in these results occur because our evaluations prioritize syntactic correctness and the strict functionality of the algorithm, whereas LLMs may focus on semantic logic, even with syntactic errors, or broader criteria, such as the quality of the test code.

For example, the implementation of Binary Search in Python produced by the **llama32** model is logically correct and functional, executing the algorithm iteratively and returning the correct index of the target element. Our manual evaluation classified the code as *Correct* since there were no logical, syntactic, or execution failures.

However, the kimi-k2-instruct-0905 model classified the submission as *Plausible*. This evaluation summary points out that “the other runnable models implemented the algorithm correctly but cluttered their test code with unused random numbers and ignored the results”. This indicates that, while recognizing the correctness of the algorithm, this model penalized the main test block for generating random data without explicitly displaying or validating the search results. Thus, kimi-k2-instruct-0905 considered aspects of style and the completeness of the implementation, while the human evaluation was restricted to the functional correctness of the algorithm, leading to a difference in judgment between plausible and correct.

5 Conclusion

In this study, we investigated the performance of algorithm implementations generated by Large Language Models (LLMs) and compared them to human-written counterparts provided by The Rosetta Code and The Algorithms across four key metrics: correctness, energy consumption, memory usage, and execution time.

Our study finds that LLMs, both those accessed via the Groq API and those integrated into code assistant applications, are highly effective at generating correct code, with average correctness rates exceeding 97%. This confirms our hypothesis that LLMs can produce reliable algorithm implementations.

⁸ These values represent the sum of *Correct*, *Plausible*, *Incorrect*, and *Invalid* implementations for these five models.

In terms of resource utilization, we conclude that the performance of LLM-generated code varies depending on the metrics, programming languages, and specific models used. While LLMs generally produce more energy-efficient algorithm implementations than human-written ones, they are not consistently superior in terms of memory usage or execution time. For example, some human-written implementations still outperform LLM-generated code in terms of memory efficiency for Python and execution time for Java. These findings highlight that the optimal choice between human-generated and LLM-generated code depends on the specific performance metric being prioritized and the programming language used. Last but not least, other factors, such as code quality, are also important for this choice. Therefore, we plan to investigate this matter in future work by measuring additional metrics, such as cyclomatic complexity.

Artifacts Availability

We provide all artifacts, such as data, tables, and graphics, in our Online Appendix [Online Appendix 2025].

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